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CONTAGIOUS AND ENVIRONMENTAL BACTERIAL SPECIES IMPLICATED IN BOVINE MASTITIS FROM SOME DAIRY FARMS IN PERAK, MALAYSIA

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Abstract: Bovine mastitis is an inflammatory condition that affects one or more quarters of the mammary gland, which is the primary site of milk production in dairy cows. The disease is commonly associated with a reduction in both milk yield and quality, leading to substantial economic losses in the dairy industry. Bacterial pathogens of both contagious and environmental origin are known as the major cause of bovine mastitis. This study aimed to determine the prevalence and distribution of bacterial species associated within selected dairy herds in Perak, Malaysia. A total of 329 composite milk samples (n = 329) were collected from 83 lactating dairy cows (n = 83) across five dairy herds. All samples were screened for mastitis using the California Mastitis Test (CMT), and CMT-positive samples were subsequently subjected to bacterial isolation and identification using analytical profile index (API) kits. Mastitis prevalence of mastitis was determined at both herd and quarter levels across all farms. The distribution of mastitis-associated pathogens, including both contagious and environmental bacteria, was also evaluated. The findings revealed a notable prevalence of mastitis among the herds under study, indicating a persistent risk to dairy productivity. Overall, mastitis remains a significant concern and may continue to contribute to considerable economic losses if effective control measures are not implemented.

Keywords: Mastitis, Dairy, Prevalence, Bacteria, CMT.

Introduction

Bovine mastitis is an inflammatory condition of the mammary gland in dairy cattle, most commonly caused by bacterial pathogens such as *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Streptococcus* species. It is recognized as one of the most prevalent and economically significant diseases affecting the global dairy

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industry. The disease occurs in both clinical and subclinical forms, with the latter being more widespread and often undetected, yet the former is responsible for substantial reductions in productivity and milk quality (Seegers et al., 2003). Mastitis has a profound economic impact on dairy production systems due to decreased milk yield, altered milk composition, increased somatic cell counts, treatment costs, and premature culling of affected animals. Collectively, these factors reduce farm profitability and efficiency. Bovine mastitis has been estimated to cause global economic losses exceeding \$35 billion annually, emphasizing its significance as a major constraint to sustainable dairy farming (Mushtaq et al., 2018; Hogeveen et al., 2011). In addition, milk from infected animals often exhibits reduced processing quality, affecting dairy product yield and safety (Halasa et al., 2007).

The burden of mastitis is particularly pronounced in tropical and developing dairy sectors, including Malaysia. Environmental conditions, such as high temperature and humidity, combined with management challenges and limited access to advanced diagnostic facilities, contribute to higher prevalence of the disease. Mastitis is considered a key factor limiting milk production and is likely one of the contributors to the country's low level of self-sufficiency in dairy supply (Kilyenyi et al, 2021).

Accurate isolation and identification of causative bacterial pathogens are essential for effective control and treatment strategies. Microbiological culture techniques using selective and differential media, alongside biochemical identification systems, remain fundamental tools in laboratory diagnosis. These methods enable targeted therapeutic interventions and inform management practices to reduce the incidence and spread of mastitis within dairy herds.

Materials and methods used

Sample Collection

To ensure the reliability of microbiological and compositional analyses, composite milk samples were collected from lactating dairy cows using a strictly aseptic technique. The study design specified the sampling unit (individual cow, udder quarter, or composite sample), timing of collection, and intended analytical procedures prior to sampling. Sampling was conducted before milking or at least 4 h after the previous milking to minimize the effects of dilution and variability in milk composition (National Mastitis Council, 2017).

California Mastitis Test

Milk samples for the test were obtained immediately before milking. The first few streams of milk (approximately two to three squirts) from each teat were discarded to eliminate contaminants and ensure representative sampling of milk from the udder cistern (Ruegg, 2017). Subsequently, a small amount of milk (approximately 2 mL) from each quarter was collected directly into the corresponding wells of a clean CMT paddle, ensuring that each of the four compartments represented a separate udder quarter.

An equal volume of the CMT reagent was added to each milk sample in the paddle. The paddle was then gently rotated in a circular motion for approximately 10–15 s to thoroughly mix the contents. Care was taken to avoid excessive agitation due to air incorporation, which could lead to false-positive results.

The reaction in each paddle compartment was immediately observed under adequate lighting and scored based on the degree of gel formation and viscosity change. The scoring system ranged from negative (no visible

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change) to trace, weak positive, distinct positive, and strong positive, corresponding to increasing somatic cell concentrations in the milk (Quinn et al., 2011).

Isolation and identification bacterial pathogens

All CMT-positive samples were inoculated onto blood and MacConkey agar, which support the growth and preliminary differentiation of bacterial organisms. Following incubation, culture plates were examined for colony morphology, hemolytic patterns on blood agar, and lactose fermentation on MacConkey agar, providing initial

Distinct colonies were selected and sub-cultured on fresh media to obtain pure isolates. These isolates were further characterized based on their cultural and morphological features, alongside preliminary observations such as Gram reaction and growth characteristics, which aid in narrowing down possible bacterial groups as described by the National Mastitis Council (Oliver, 2004).

Pure isolates were analyzed using API identification kits, consisting of standardized biochemical micro tests, for definitive identification. Bacterial suspensions were introduced into the test strips, and following incubation, colorimetric changes were observed and recorded. These results were converted into numerical profiles and interpreted using established identification databases to determine the bacterial species according to the API (Biomérieux, France) following the manufacturer's guidelines.

The final identification was achieved by correlating the cultural characteristics observed on selective and differential media with the biochemical profiles obtained from the API system, ensuring the accurate identification of the bacterial pathogens (CLSI, 2020).

Results

The recorded cow level prevalence was 93.3% (14/15), 73.3% (11/15), 100% (16/16), 100% (21/21), and 43.8% 7/16 for farms A, B, C, D and E, respectively (Table 1).

Likewise, the quarter-level prevalence rates of mastitis were recorded as 76.6% (46/60), 38.3% (23/60), 100% (64/64), 39.8% (33/83) and 24.2% (15/62) for farm A, B, C, D and E, respectively (Table 1).

Of the total 181 CMT-positive samples, 138 (76.2%) were culture positive. The identified bacterial pathogens associated with mastitis from these farms were *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (11.6%), *Actinobacter baumannii* (11.6%), Coagulase-negative staphylococci (CoNS) (8.8%), *Enterobacter cloacae* (8.5%), *Escherichia coli* (6.6%), *Streptococcus uberis* (5.5%), *Pseudomonas spp* (5.5%), and *Staphylococcus aureus* (4.4%).

Others included were other streptococci sp. (5.5%), *Pantoea spp* (2.2%), *Citrobacter spp* (2.2%), *Enterococcus spp* (1.7%) and yeast (1.1%) (Table 2).

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Table 1 Results of the California mastitis test (CMT) of the quarter and cow level prevalence of mastitis from selected dairy farms.

Farms	Number of Quarter samples collected	Number of quarterly samples positive	Percentage of quarter samples positive (%)	Number of cows sampled	Number of cows positive	Percentage of cows positive (%)
A	60	46	76.6	15	14	93.3
B	60	23	38.3	15	11	73.3
C	64	64	100	16	16	100
D	83	33	39.8	21	21	100
E	62	15	24.2	16	7	43.8
Total	329	181	-	83	69	-

Table 2 Distribution of mastitis-associated bacterial pathogens from selected dairy farms

Pathogens	No. of isolated pathogens	Percentage (%)
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	8	4.4
Coagulase-negative staphylococci	16	8.8
<i>E. coli</i>	12	6.6
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	21	11.6
<i>Streptococcus agalactiae</i>	1	0.6
<i>Streptococcus uberis</i>	10	5.5
Other streptococcus sp.	10	5.5
Enterobacter sp.	15	8.5
Pantoea sp.	4	2.2
Micrococcus sp.	1	0.6
Citrobacter sp.	4	2.2
Pseudomonas sp.	10	5.5
Yeast	2	1.1
Enterococcus sp.	3	1.7
<i>Actinobacter baumannii</i>	21	11.6
Culture negative	43	23.4
Total	181	100

Discussion

High prevalence rates of subclinical bovine mastitis have previously been reported in Malaysian dairy herds, highlighting its persistent and widespread nature within tropical production systems (Murugaiyah et al., 2014). Subclinical mastitis is particularly problematic because it lacks obvious clinical signs, allowing infections to remain undetected while continuously reducing milk yield and quality. Consequently, it contributes significantly to hidden economic losses in dairy farming. Several studies have identified mastitis, especially the

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subclinical form, as one of the most economically burdensome diseases affecting dairy herds globally (Abebe et al., 2016; Halasa et al., 2007).

In the present study, a high overall prevalence (76.2%) of mastitis-associated pathogens including environmental organisms such as coagulase-negative staphylococci (CoNS) and coliforms, as well as contagious pathogens including *Staphylococcus aureus*, was observed. This finding aligns with previous reports indicating that the epidemiology of mastitis is often multifactorial, involving a combination of environmental and contagious agents (Azevedo et al., 2016; Bradley, 2002). CoNS have increasingly been recognized as important emerging pathogens in subclinical mastitis due to their ability to persist in the udder and evade host immune responses, while coliforms are commonly associated with environmental contamination, particularly in poorly managed housing systems (Taponen & Pyörälä, 2009). *S. aureus* remains a major contagious pathogen known for its chronicity, resistance to treatment, and ability to spread during milking (Barkema et al., 2006).

The detection of these pathogens in milk raises important public health concerns. Consumption of raw or inadequately pasteurized milk contaminated with mastitis-causing bacteria may lead to foodborne and zoonotic infections. Enterotoxins can be produced by pathogens such as *S. aureus*, while certain coliforms, including pathogenic strains of *Escherichia coli*, are associated with gastrointestinal illness in humans (Oliver et al., 2005). This underscores the importance of proper milk handling, pasteurization, and herd health management to safeguard the health consumer health.

The high prevalence observed in this study can be attributed to a combination of risk factors. Poor milking hygiene, inadequate equipment sanitation, and lack of routine screening programs facilitate the transmission of contagious pathogens within herds. Additionally, environmental factors such as high humidity and temperature, which are common in tropical regions such as Malaysia, create favorable conditions for the proliferation of environmental bacteria (Abebe et al., 2016; Zeryehun & Abera, 2017). Animal-related factors, such as parity, lactation stage, and immune status, also influence susceptibility to infection.

Overall, these findings reinforce the need for integrated mastitis control strategies, including improved farm management practices, regular monitoring of udder health, and accurate identification of causative pathogens. Such measures are essential to reduce the prevalence of mastitis, minimize economic losses, and mitigate associated public health risks.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the prevalence of bovine mastitis across all herds examined was considerable and is likely to continue contributing to significant economic losses within dairy production systems. The findings indicated that the primary sources of mastitis-causing pathogens are the cows' immediate environment and contaminated milking equipment, which facilitate both environmental and contagious transmission.

Therefore, effective mastitis control depends largely on improving farm management practices. Enhanced hygiene during milking, proper sanitation of equipment, and improved housing and bedding management are critical measures for reducing pathogen exposure. The Implementation of these strategies can significantly lower the incidence of mastitis, thereby improving milk quality and yield while minimizing associated economic losses.

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